

PERCEPTUAL FACTORS AND USER EXPERIENCE: RESEARCH ON THE MEDIATING ROLE OF INNOVATION IN VoiBook SPEECH REHABILITATION APPLICATION

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Abstract

This research aims to explore the significant impact of perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived value on the user experience of hearing-impaired users using the VoiBook speech rehabilitation application under the mediation of innovation. Based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Means-end Theory, combined with Social Learning Theory, three hypotheses were proposed. User data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using the PLS-SEM method. The results show that perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived value all significantly affect user experience through innovation, providing a theoretical basis and practical suggestions for improving the design and promotion of speech rehabilitation applications.

Keywords: Perceived Ease of Use; Perceived Usefulness; Perceived Value; Innovation; User Experience; VoiBook Speech Rehabilitation Application.

1. BACKGROUND OF INDUSTRY

With the rapid development of information technology and the continuous enrichment of digital education resources, mobile learning applications have become increasingly important in the field of speech rehabilitation education. However, current research and application development often ignore the unique needs of hearing-impaired user groups. Research has found that the group currently in high demand for hearing impairment training is the youth group. They grew up in the rapidly developing Internet era, are full of curiosity about new technologies and networks, and strive to integrate into China's rapidly developing era of networked life, education, and learning. However, it is trapped in practical blind spots, technical obstacles, and cultural differences in the application of information accessibility technology (Wu Weihua, 2023). Most are still struggling to find cultural and social participation opportunities that suit them and face the risk and discrimination of being marginalized as the lower middle class of information daily (Kang Kun, 2019).

In this context, the development of the VoiBook application is precisely to meet the special needs of the hearing-impaired group. Detailed research of the usage of VoiBook users can not only reveal the behavioral patterns of hearing-impaired users on the mobile speech learning platform but also provide an in-depth understanding of their experience needs and preferences during use, thereby improving the user stickiness of the product. "A large number of scholars cannot do without studying user experience when studying user stickiness. There is a correlation between user experience and user stickiness. A good user experience will trigger continuous usage behavior and promote the improvement of user stickiness. User experience

is the basis for users to decide whether to leave or stay" (Zhu Feng, 2020). This type of research is of great value in guiding the design and optimization of special applications for hearing-impaired users, helping to improve the rehabilitation experience and learning outcomes of this group and enhancing users' willingness to continue using such products.

In order to optimize user experience, this study explores the significant impact of perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and perceived value on user experience through innovation based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Means-end Theory and Social Learning Theory.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

2.1 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was proposed by Fred D. Davis in 1989, aiming to explain how users accept and use a new technology (Davis, 1989). TAM is one of the important theories in the field of understanding information system user acceptance behavior. It was developed based on Fishbein and Ajzen's Theory of Reasoned Behavior (TRB). Since the technology acceptance model was proposed, domestic and foreign scholars have widely used it in the field of education. It has become an important theoretical basis for explaining and predicting people's acceptance of emerging information technologies in education (Xu Shun, 2020). The Technology Acceptance Model includes four core constructs: Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Attitude Toward Using, and Behavioral Intention toward Use. Perceived Usefulness refers to the degree to which a user believes that using a specific system or new technology will enhance their job performance or expected work efficiency. Perceived Ease of Use refers to the degree to which a user believes that using the system will be effortless. Attitude Toward Using refers to the user's positive or negative subjective attitude towards adopting new technology or systems. Behavioral Intention to Use refers to the user's willingness to use new technology or systems, which is also a subjective expression of intention. These, along with external variables and system use, constitute the basic structure of the Technology Acceptance Model. Among them, Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use directly affect the user's attitude toward use and intention to use, which in turn affects the actual use behavior.

This model believes that whether to use the system is determined by the user's behavioral intention. The user's behavioral intention is determined by the attitude towards use and perceived usefulness. The attitude towards use is determined by the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. The perceived usefulness is determined by the perceived ease of use. Usability and external variables are determined, and perceived ease of use is determined by external variables. External variables mainly refer to the design characteristics of the system itself. This model is mainly used to research whether system users accept and adopt technological behaviors. It has a simple structure and has become a hot spot in the field of organizational behavior research (Zhang Lu, 2021). TAM reveals a set of general factors influencing user acceptance of information systems, effectively explaining and predicting user attitudes and behavioral performance towards information systems.

Fig 2.1: Technology Acceptance Model, by Davis,1989

Research indicates that TAM is supported by a large body of empirical studies, capable of explaining 40% of the variance in individual behavioral intentions, showcasing a clear advantage over other corresponding theoretical models (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000).

The TAM model focuses on the initial adoption behavior of information systems, while the continued use behavior of users is a continuation after the initial adoption. As research continues to deepen, as one of the most widely used theories to explain user behavior, many studies have tried to modify and extend TAM on the original architecture by combining other theoretical models or adding new external variables, belief variables, etc., to It should be used in the research of continued user usage (Thomas et al., 2011).

TAM is a relatively streamlined model, providing a main thread for subsequent research: the user's behavior towards new technology depends on the user's behavioral intention. Applying the Technology Acceptance Model to the analysis of the continued use behavior of speech rehabilitation application users and exploring the various issues faced by the hearing-impaired user group in accepting and using information services is beneficial.

It helps in identifying and improving the shortcomings of information services in the development and use of speech rehabilitation applications, enhancing the service quality of speech rehabilitation application products.

2.2 Means-end Theory

The Means-End Theory was initially proposed by psychologist Milton Rokeach, with Reynold & Gutman completing its theoretical foundation. The Means-End Theory is a simple intentional structure that connects attributes, consequences, and values (J Gutman, 1982). That is, consumers' product knowledge stems from their cognition of product attributes; the results generated from use may help consumers attain their ultimate values.

The theory contends that consumers attribute value to product attributes not because of the attributes themselves but because of the attributes' ability to help consumers achieve their desired outcomes (J Gutman, 1982). These attributes can be understood as characteristics of a product; the consequences can be seen as benefits arising from the use of this product; values represent the ultimate goals important to the consumer or the motivation for using the product.

The Means-End Theory refers to the method of interviewing and analyzing consumers in terms of interrelated outcomes to understand the reasons behind their decisions and to comprehend these responses (Reynolds & Colson, 2001).

This approach indicates that people choose products because they possess attributes (means) that are critical for achieving anticipated results and realizing values (ends) (Vero Vanden Abeele, 2012). Additionally, Olson and Peter report that people have three levels of knowledge related to products, namely: product attributes, the consequences of using the product, and the values (or goals) that can be achieved with the product (Peter & Olson, 2010)

In the context of this research, the means-ends theory helps explain the behavioral motivations and decision-making process of hearing-impaired users when using the VoiBook speech rehabilitation app. Specifically, users form perceived value after weighing the cost of using the VoiBook app (such as learning difficulty and operational complexity) and the benefits (such as speech training effects and functional practicality).

When users believe that the VoiBook app can provide significant practical value and meet their speech rehabilitation needs, the increase in perceived value will stimulate users' innovative behavior and constantly explore new ways of use to optimize their own experience. This theoretical perspective provides an important basis for studying the relationship between perceived value and innovation, and provides new theoretical support for understanding the formation mechanism of user experience.

2.3 Social Learning Theory and Innovation

Albert Bandura first explicitly introduced Social Learning Theory (SLT) in 1971 (Bandura, 1971), with its core idea being that people observe and learn or imitate others' behaviors, and then strengthen or weaken these behaviors according to self-established standards.

Social Learning Theory explains how people learn and adapt to new things by observing and imitating the behavior of others. In this research, this theory provides a valuable perspective by analyzing the use of speech rehabilitation applications by hearing-impaired users, especially how they accept and use new features by observing and imitating the innovative behaviors of others.

By deeply studying the feedback and behavior patterns of users in social interactions, the research can better understand which innovative features can attract users, to design and promote these features in a targeted manner and increase the attractiveness and usage rate of the application. The application of social learning theory not only helps to reveal the learning and acceptance process of users, but also provides a practical basis for product improvement to ensure its success in a highly competitive market.

As an important theory for explaining human imitative and learning behaviors, Social Learning Theory (SLT) has been widely applied across various fields. To help people understand the basic content and current application status of SLT, scholars have reviewed the existing literature from two aspects:

On the one hand, the organization of basic content, theoretical development, and empirical status. Wu Gang and others mainly expounded on the theory's basic content, development, and application from four aspects: SLT's main views, application fields, research dimensions, and theoretical evolution (Wu Gang, 2018).

Based on the introduction of the theory, Kruis N. E., and others conducted empirical tests on SLT's concept regarding substance use (Kruis N E, 2020), while Pratt T. C. and others evaluated its empirical status through a meta-analysis of SLT-related empirical literature over the past thirty years (Travis C. Pratt, 2009).

On the other hand, the organization of specific domain application research. Kang Jian reviewed the research on investment decisions and summarized the influence of SLT on rational herd behavior (Kang Jian, 2009). In sociology, SLT is often used to research human behavior. Chavis A. M. proposed a method for dealing with human behavior that combines structural and practical aspects based on SLT and highlighted the effectiveness of following the theory and its methods (A. Chavis, 2011).

Regarding criminal behavior, Tittle C. R. mainly elaborated on the evolutionary process of SLT in application (Tittle, 2004). Furthermore, scholars have organized research in the field of education, with Hill J. R. and others considering context, culture, community, and learner characteristics as influencing factors in teaching, proposing the formulation of effective design principles, promoting social interactive learning, and examining individual learner characteristics (Janette R. Hill, 2009). Bahn D., focusing on nursing education, emphasized the importance of observational learning and imitation of others during the learning process (Bahn, 2001).

In the field of information systems, issues such as the impact of subject behavior on the continuous use of information systems and consumer purchase intentions can be explained based on the perspectives of observational learning, triadic interaction, self-regulation, and self-efficacy from Social Learning Theory (SLT). Consequently, application research of SLT in the field of information systems has begun to attract widespread attention from the academic community, resulting in the emergence of some valuable research findings.

In this research, innovation refers to the process in which users use the VoiBook speech rehabilitation application, through continuous exploration and experimentation, to discover the most suitable usage method for their own needs, to improve the overall user experience. This innovative behavior not only includes self-learning and adaptation of application functions, but also includes personalized operation and optimization in specific situations to obtain better speech training effects.

According to Social Learning Theory, users' innovative behavior stems from active exploration and practice of application systems, and continuously optimizes their usage methods through feedback and reinforcement mechanisms. This innovative behavior helps to enhance users' satisfaction and experience perception of the technical system, thereby significantly improving users' willingness to use and dependence on the VoiBook application.

In this process, users' innovative behavior is not only an active application of the technical system, but also a self-satisfaction and improvement of their own needs, which provides important theoretical support for understanding the formation mechanism of user experience.

2.4 Hypothesis

In this research, we proposed three core hypotheses based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Means-end Theory, and Social Learning Theory to explore the significant impact of perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived value on user experience under the influence of innovation.

H1: Perceived ease of use has a significant impact on the user experience through the mediating effect of Innovation.

Perceived ease of use refers to the perceived ease of operation and learning difficulty of a system or technology when the user uses it. In the VoiBook speech rehabilitation application, perceived ease of use represents the user's subjective judgment on the intuitiveness and simplicity of interface design, functional layout, and interactive operation during use. The technology acceptance model believes that higher perceived ease of use can effectively improve users' acceptance and willingness to use the system. Under the mediating role of innovation, when users find that the use of the application is simpler and easier to understand during the process of exploration and trial, their user experience will be significantly improved.

H2: Perceived usefulness has a significant impact on the user experience through the mediating effect of Innovation.

Perceived usefulness is the degree to which users believe that using a system or technology can improve their task performance. In this study, perceived usefulness is mainly reflected in the fact that when users use the VoiBook application for speech rehabilitation training, they believe that the application can effectively help improve pronunciation and communication skills. The technology acceptance model shows that when users perceive the actual utility of the system, they will show higher satisfaction and willingness to use. Through innovative behavior, users can explore more suitable usage methods and training modes for themselves, thereby further enhancing perceived usefulness and improving user experience.

H3: Perceived value has a significant impact on the user experience through the mediating effect of Innovation.

Perceived value refers to the trade-off and judgment between the user's input and benefits when using a system. The means-end theory emphasizes that when users use technology, they will make a comprehensive evaluation of the value of the application system based on their own needs and expectations.

In the context of the VoiBook application, perceived value includes not only functional utility, but also the emotional satisfaction and psychological recognition that users obtain in speech rehabilitation training. When users find the best way to use the app through innovative behaviors or achieve significant results during training, the perceived value will be further enhanced, thereby improving the user experience.

In summary, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived value are key factors affecting user experience. By introducing innovation as a mediating variable, this study explores how the exploration and optimization behaviors of users in the process of using the VoiBook application regulate the impact of these perceived factors on user experience.

H1: Perceived ease of use has a significant impact on the user experience through the mediating effect of Innovation.

H2: Perceived usefulness has a significant impact on the user experience through the mediating effect of Innovation.

H3: Perceived value has a significant impact on the user experience through the mediating effect of Innovation.

The proposal of these three hypotheses provides a theoretical basis and guiding direction for subsequent empirical research.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This research chose the quantitative approach in the mono method, which has an important impact on the design and implementation of the research. Through the mono-quantitative approach, this research can systematically measure and analyze the key factors of hearing-impaired people using the "VOIBOOK" speech rehabilitation application, verify hypotheses, and test theoretical frameworks through statistical methods.

This section will elaborate on why the mono-quantitative approach was chosen and how it played a role in the research. This research adopted a quantitative research method, aiming to systematically collect and analyze data on the use experience of speech rehabilitation applications by hearing-impaired users and their willingness to continue using them.

Quantitative research methods can reveal the relationship between variables and test research hypotheses through structured data collection tools and statistical analysis techniques. The advantages of quantitative research are its objectivity, repeatability, and universal applicability, which makes the research results highly scientific and reliable (SIS, 2024).

Quantitative research is a method of studying phenomena by collecting and analyzing numerical data. Its characteristics include structured data collection, statistical analysis, objectivity, and repeatability.

The definition and characteristics of quantitative research methods are as follows: Structured data collection uses questionnaires, experiments, and other tools to collect data according to a predetermined structure to ensure the uniformity and comparability of data; statistical analysis analyzes data through mathematical and statistical methods to reveal the relationship and law between variables; researchers remain neutral, and the data collection and analysis process avoids subjective bias as much as possible; the research design and methods are clear, and other researchers can repeat the research process to verify the reliability of the results (Wang Wenxia, 2016).

3.1 Characteristics of Quantitative Research Methods

Quantitative Research Method is a research method based on digitalization and objective measurement. It emphasizes revealing the relationship between variables through numerical and statistical analysis. Quantitative research usually uses structured questionnaires, quantitative data collection, and analysis, to verify hypotheses or theories and find causal relationships. The quantitative method was chosen for this research because it can accurately and reliably capture and analyze the use behavior of the hearing-impaired people on the "VOIBOOK" application, thereby revealing the relationship between perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived value, innovation, technology and user experience.

Quantitative research methods have a few significant advantages that were critical in this research:

Measurability and objectivity: Quantitative research emphasizes the measurability of data and can provide clear conclusions through numerical and statistical models to reduce subjective bias. This research objectively evaluates the usage behavior of hearing-impaired people through quantitative indicators such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, user experience scores, etc.

Large and representative sample size: Quantitative research is usually able to cover a large sample size and ensure representativeness of the sample through random sampling or stratified sampling. This research uses a questionnaire survey method to collect a large amount of data from the hearing-impaired population in Shanghai to ensure the breadth and representativeness of the data, thereby improving the external validity of the research results.

Efficiency of data analysis: Quantitative research methods allow complex variable relationship analysis through statistical techniques such as regression analysis and structural equation modeling (SEM). This research can use these methods to analyze the relationship between independent variables (perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived value), mediating variables (innovation), moderating variables (technology) and dependent variables (user experience).

Applicability of quantitative research: This research aims to explore the key factors that affect the use of the "VOIBOOK" application by the hearing-impaired population, especially to verify a series of theoretical frameworks and hypotheses, including the technology acceptance model, user experience theory, social learning theory, and means-end theory. Because these theoretical frameworks involve interactive relationships between multiple variables, quantitative research methods provide an ideal tool for studying these relationships. By collecting structured data, researchers can use statistical methods to test hypotheses and make reliable inferences at the theoretical level.

3.2 Mono Method Selection

In the methodological selection, researchers can adopt a single method (Mono Method), a multi-method (multi-Method) or a mixed method (Mixed-Method). This research chose the quantitative method in the mono method, that is, answering the research questions only through

quantitative data collection and analysis. The advantage of a mono method is its focus and consistency. By choosing only quantitative methods, this research can focus all its energy on building rigorous statistical models and data analysis, avoiding the complexity of integrating different data sources that may appear in mixed methods.

Method consistency: A mono method can ensure a high degree of consistency between research methods and data analysis. All data come from the same type of source-structured questionnaires, which simplifies the data processing process and the construction of analysis models.

Simplified research design: Compared with mixed methods, a mono method can simplify the research design. Researchers only need to focus on how to design efficient questionnaires, how to collect quantitative data, and how to conduct statistical analysis. This saves time and resources for the implementation of the research and reduces potential research bias.

Data comparability: Through a single quantitative data collection method, all variables in this research are measured with the same standard, which makes it easier to compare and analyze the relationship between different variables. For example, the numerical processing of variables such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and perceived value enables the interactions between them to be explored in depth through regression analysis, SEM, and other methods.

Although multi-method and mixed methods may help to integrate multiple data sources in some studies, the main reasons for not using these methods in this research are:

Singleness of research purpose: The main purpose of this research is to verify and explain the key factors of hearing-impaired people using the "VOIBOOK" application, rather than to explore the deep cognitive or emotional experience behind these factors. Quantitative research methods are already able to fully answer these questions, so there is no need to introduce qualitative methods to gain additional insights.

Time and resource limitations: Mixed methods require the collection and analysis of multiple types of data, such as qualitative interviews and quantitative questionnaires. This will increase the complexity of data collection and analysis and require more time and resources. This research aims to answer research questions quickly and effectively through quantitative data, so a single quantitative method is more practical.

Reducing complexity: Quantitative methods themselves can already handle complex variable relationships through precise statistical tools, while mixed methods may introduce more unnecessary complexity.

3.3 Quantitative Data Collection in Research Implementation

This research collected data through a questionnaire survey. The questionnaire consists of multiple parts, each of which measures different variables, such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived value, innovation, and user experience. To ensure the validity and reliability of the data, each question in the questionnaire was rigorously designed and pre-tested to ensure that they can accurately capture the feedback of the target respondents.

The questionnaire design follows standard quantitative research specifications. Each question is scored using a Likert scale, and respondents can rate their perceptions on a scale of 1 to 5, such as "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree".

This scale helps quantify the subjective feelings of respondents into analyzable numerical data. Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use: These questions are designed to understand respondents' views on the functionality and difficulty of using the "VOIBOOK" application. For example, users may be asked "Do you think the app is helpful for your speech training?" or "Do you think the app is easy to use?" Perceived value: Questions will involve users' subjective evaluation of the value of the app, such as "Do you think the app is worth the money overall?"

User experience: Questions in this section focus on users' overall experience perception of the app, including satisfaction and user friendliness.

The target group of this research is the hearing-impaired population in Shanghai, so the key step in data collection is to ensure that this specific group can be reached. The researchers distributed the questionnaires through cooperative institutions and relevant community organizations. To ensure the representativeness of the data, the researchers adopted a random sampling method and paid attention to the diversity of the sample, such as the age, gender, and educational background of the respondents.

3.4 Data Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

After the data collection was completed, the researchers analyzed the data using SPSS statistical software. Specific analysis methods include:

Descriptive statistical analysis: First, understand the overall situation of the data through descriptive statistics, such as the basic information of the respondents, the mean and standard deviation of each variable, etc.

Regression analysis: used to test the direct impact of independent variables on dependent variables, such as the impact of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on user experience.

Structural equation model (SEM): used to analyze complex variable path relationships, especially the role of mediating variables (innovation) and moderating variables (technology).

This research adopted a single quantitative research method to explore the key factors that affect the use of the "VOIBOOK" application by the hearing-impaired population through precise measurement and rigorous statistical analysis.

Through the choice of Mono Method Quantitative, the research can simplify the design, improve the operability of the research, and ensure the accuracy and reliability of data analysis. This method is not only suitable for the objectives and hypothesis verification of this research, but also provides a solid theoretical foundation for future application research.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In this research, the data analysis process includes data preprocessing, reliability and validity testing, structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis, and hypothesis verification. To ensure the accuracy and effectiveness of data analysis, this study used SPSS and PLS-SEM software for statistical analysis and model construction. The specific steps and results of data analysis will be described in detail below.

4.1 Data preprocessing

After data collection was completed, all questionnaire data were preliminarily sorted and cleaned. First, invalid questionnaires that were incomplete or filled out with obvious regularity were eliminated. Then, the remaining valid questionnaires were coded and standardized for subsequent statistical analysis. In this study, all variables were measured using a five-point Likert scale, where "1" means "strongly disagree" and "5" means "strongly agree".

Data standardization includes uniform coding of variable names and conversion of text variables into numerical variables. During data input and coding, the study paid special attention to maintaining data consistency and accuracy. After preliminary screening and sorting, a total of 385 valid questionnaire data were obtained, providing sufficient sample support for subsequent analysis.

4.2 Reliability and validity test

Before conducting structural equation model analysis, it is necessary to test the reliability and validity of the measurement tool to ensure the adaptability of the model and the validity of the results.

4.2.1 Reliability Test

The reliability test is used to evaluate the internal consistency of the scale, that is, the consistency of each measurement item when measuring the same latent variable. This study uses Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR) as indicators of reliability test.

In Cronbach's Alpha analysis, it is generally believed that when the α value is greater than 0.7, the reliability of the scale is good; when the α value is greater than 0.8, the reliability is excellent. In the composite reliability (CR) analysis, when the CR value is greater than 0.7, it indicates that the internal consistency of the latent variable is high.

In this study, the Cronbach's Alpha values of each latent variable (perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, perceived value, innovation, and user experience) are all greater than 0.7, and the CR values are all higher than 0.7, indicating that the scale has good reliability.

4.2.2 Validity test

Validity test mainly includes convergent validity and discriminant validity.

Convergent validity is measured by average variance extracted (AVE). When the AVE value is greater than 0.5, it means that the latent variable has good convergent validity. Discriminant validity is tested by the Fornell-Larcker criterion and cross-loading matrix. If the square root

of the AVE of a latent variable is greater than its correlation coefficient with other latent variables, it has good discriminant validity. The research results show that the AVE values of all latent variables are greater than 0.5, and the square root of the AVE of each latent variable is greater than the correlation coefficient with other latent variables, indicating that the scale has good convergent validity and discriminant validity.

4.3 Structural equation model analysis

This research uses partial least squares (PLS-SEM) to construct and verify the hypothesis model. PLS-SEM is suitable for studies with small sample sizes and relatively complex models, and can effectively handle reflective and formative constructs. The model analysis process includes a model fit test and path coefficient analysis.

4.3.1 Model fit test

The structural model was tested for fit by PLS-SEM, mainly using the following indicators:

R^2 (coefficient of determination): reflects the degree of explanation of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The larger the R^2 value, the stronger the explanatory power of the model.

Q^2 (prediction correlation): evaluates the predictive ability of the model by cross-validation method. When the Q^2 value is greater than 0, it indicates that the model has good predictive power.

SRMR (standardized root mean square residual): used to evaluate the goodness of fit of the model. When the SRMR value is less than 0.08, it indicates that the model fits well. The results show that the structural model of this study has good fit and predictive power, the R^2 values are within the acceptable range, the Q^2 value is positive, and the SRMR value is less than 0.08, indicating that the model fits well.

4.3.2 Path coefficient analysis and hypothesis verification

Based on the model fit test, the significance of each path was tested. The path coefficient was estimated and tested for significance by using the Bootstrap sampling method (5000 times). This research verified the path coefficients and significance levels of hypotheses H1, H2, and H3 through the structural equation model to explore the impact of perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived value on user experience under the influence of innovation.

H1: Perceived ease of use has a significant impact on the user experience through the mediating effect of Innovation.

The results of the path analysis show that the path coefficient of perceived ease of use on innovation is 0.151, the t-value is 2.922, and the p-value is 0.003. The significance level is less than 0.05, indicating that the path is statistically significant. In addition, the direct path coefficient of perceived ease of use on user experience is 0.144, the t-value is 3.058, and the p-value is 0.002, which is also significant. The results of the study verified hypothesis H1, indicating that when users think that the VoiBook application is easy to use, their innovative behavior is more likely to be stimulated, and this innovative behavior can significantly improve

the user experience. This finding is consistent with the theoretical assumptions of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), indicating that perceived ease of use not only directly affects the user experience, but also indirectly promotes the improvement of the user experience through innovative behavior.

H2: Perceived usefulness has a significant impact on the user experience through the mediating effect of Innovation.

The path coefficient between perceived usefulness and innovation is 0.244, the t-value is 4.46, and the p-value is 0.000, showing a very high significance. The direct path coefficient of perceived usefulness to user experience is 0.162, the t value is 3.199, and the p-value is 0.001. These results support hypothesis H2, indicating that when users perceive the VoiBook application to be practical and effective in speech rehabilitation training, they are more inclined to generate innovative behavior and improve the user experience in the process. Perceived usefulness not only indirectly affects the user experience through innovation, but also has a significant direct impact on the user experience. This finding further supports the core role of perceived usefulness in the technology acceptance model on user behavior and experience.

H3: Perceived value has a significant impact on the user experience through the mediating effect of Innovation.

The path coefficient between perceived value and innovation is 0.263, the t-value is 5.5, and the p-value is 0.000, indicating that there is a highly significant positive relationship between the two. At the same time, the direct path coefficient of perceived value on user experience is 0.103, the t-value is 1.989, and the p-value is 0.047, reaching the significance standard. The verification results support hypothesis H3, that is, when users use the VoiBook application, the higher the positive perception formed after weighing its actual value and cost, the more likely it is to stimulate innovative behavior and improve user experience under the influence of innovative behavior. This finding echoes the Means-end Theory, indicating that users' innovative behavior stems from the recognition of perceived value, and achieves a better user experience through the exploration and optimization of innovative behavior. Overall, H1, H2, and H3 are all supported by the data, and the path coefficients and significance levels all indicate that perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived value have a significant positive impact on the user experience through innovative behavior. This result not only verifies the applicability of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the means-end theory, but also provides a theoretical basis and practical reference for the application of VoiBook among hearing-impaired users.

5. CONCLUSION

This research explores the relationship between perceptual factors (perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived value) and user experience, focusing on the mediating role of innovation in this relationship. Through the empirical analysis of the structural equation model (SEM), the applicability of the technology acceptance model (TAM), means-end theory, and social learning theory was verified. The results show that perceived ease of use, perceived

usefulness, and perceived value all significantly affect user experience through innovation, thus verifying the validity of hypotheses H1, H2, and H3.

Specifically, perceived ease of use significantly affects users' innovative behavior, and this innovative behavior can significantly improve user experience. This shows that when users perceive the ease of use of the VoiBook application, they are more likely to conduct autonomous exploration and innovation, thereby improving their user experience. Perceived usefulness also shows a significant positive effect. When users believe that the application can effectively support voice rehabilitation training, the frequency and quality of innovative behavior will increase, thereby improving user experience. The significant impact of perceived value is also verified, indicating that when users weigh the actual value and cost of the application, the higher the perceived value, the more likely users are to actively innovate to optimize the use effect and obtain a better experience. In addition, the results show that innovation plays a significant mediating role between perception factors and user experience. This finding is consistent with the expectations of social learning theory, that is, users continuously adjust and optimize the use of applications through innovative behaviors to meet their own needs and improve satisfaction. Therefore, innovation is not only the result of user experience, but also an important path to enhance user experience.

The theoretical contribution of this study is that it reveals the key role of perception factors in innovation by integrating the technology acceptance model and the means-end theory, and verifies the mediating effect of innovation between perception factors and user experience. The practical contribution is that it provides important theoretical support and practical guidance for the optimization and promotion of VoiBook speech rehabilitation applications. Future research can further explore the performance and impact of innovative behaviors in different situations and user groups to improve this theoretical framework and enhance the universality and practicality of applications.

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